

New frontiers in separation processes & membranes development

In Johannesburg, 17 to 19 July 2019

3-day workshop

at the University of Johannesburg
School of Tourism & Hospitality conference room

UNESCO Chair
"Membrane Science applied for Environment",
University of Montpellier
(Chemistry School of Engineering)

A workshop based on a bilateral partnership between South Africa & France, to provide a platform for various stakeholders interested in **improving the quality of water & air in South Africa**

Booklet of abstracts

With the participation & support of

New frontiers in separation processes & membranes development

A bilateral workshop South Africa – France, Johannesburg, 17-19 July 2019

On behalf of the organizing committee, the partners and sponsors, it is a pleasure to extend to you a personal welcome to the 2019 UJ-UM workshop. This workshop, which we believe is the first of a series to come, has a triple purpose:

- To disseminate broad technical knowledge in the field of separation processes and membrane development.
- To promote interactive exchanges between participants interested in real life applications
- To promote sustainable collaboration between the researchers at the University of Montpellier and the University of Johannesburg.

For this year, we choose to focus on air and water quality in urban, rural and industrial areas, which are two national and also global environmental challenges.

The access to safe drinking water all around the world and especially in South Africa is more and more limited due to population growth, climate change and environmental water pollution by sewage, industrial effluents, chemicals, domestic wastes and pesticides, etc. In the same vein, air pollution in urban and industrial areas due to automotive exhaust gases, mining and industrial activities, is an awkward defy.

A panel of highly esteemed experts from the academia and industry will share their expertise, and debate solutions to water and air quality challenges. Please join our panelists every day as they address social, political and economic questions affecting water and air quality in South Africa.

I trust you will find the workshop both valuable and enjoyable.

Prof. Xavier Y. MBIANDA

Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Johannesburg
Workshop coordinator

The UNESCO Chair SIMEV greatly appreciates being associated with the organization of this first French/South African event and wishes to thank the University of Johannesburg for its invitation. In the framework offered to her, the SIMEV Chair has chosen to set up a new STM school on the theme: "Sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes- Energy supply". This is a topic of great importance for the well-being of people living outside the urban context in South Africa, but also in many other developing countries in Africa or other continents. Indeed, to treat water and effluents with membrane technologies to make them drinkable and reusable, preferably using renewable energy (solar, wind) is a major challenge of this century.

To share scientific knowledge to learn from each other, to address together problems difficult to approach separately through new collaborative actions, to find the means to carry out concrete solutions: here are some of the main objectives of Membrane Thematic Schools (STM), an original SIMEV tool of which this is the 18th edition.

I wish all of you a fruitful work and a lot of future joint actions.

Prof. Gilbert M. RIOS

President of the UNESCO SIMEV Chair

New frontiers in separation processes & membranes development

Detailed Program of the workshop

Wednesday, July 17

8:00 to 8:55 *Welcoming and installation of the delegates*

Words of Welcome

by University of Johannesburg Officials / French High commission representatives/ DST Representatives

Chair: Prof Debra MEYER (Executive Dean Faculty of Sciences - University of Johannesburg)

9:10 to 9:20 **Professor Saurabh SINHA** - Deputy vice Chancellor Research of the University of Johannesburg

9:20 to 9:30 **Mr Mathieu BECUE** - Attaché for Innovation - French Embassy in South Africa

9:30 to 9:40 **Mr Khaya SISHUBA** - Director: Bilateral Relations - Europe & Gulf States, Department of Science and Technology

9:40 to 10:00 **Steps to advance membrane & filtration sciences in Africa: Perspectives from the African Membrane Society.** *Invited speaker: Dr Abdoulaye DOUCOURE, AMSIC*

10:00 to 10:45 *Group picture & coffee break*

Global environmental protection - Water quality in urban areas

Presentation of SA challenges – focus on large-scale issues

Chair/Moderators: A.Prof. R. MOUTLOALI & Prof MIELE

Time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation / Institute
10:50 to 11:10	Non-occupational environmental risk assessment from exposure to mercury in the gold mining environment of Witwatersrand basin, South Africa. <i>Invited speaker: Sylvester NKWE</i>	NGO.
11:10 to 11:30	Treatment of Brine for the Recovery of Drinking Water, Calcium Carbonate and Sodium Sulphate. <i>Invited speaker: Dr Munyaradzi MUJURU</i>	University of Limpopo
11:30 to 11:50	Circular Economy Model For Water And Wastewater Management <i>Invited speaker: Dr John Ngoni ZVIMBA</i>	Water research Commission
11:50 to 12:10	Water Treatment Technologies Research and Development at the DST/Mintek Nanotechnology Innovation Centre. <i>Invited speaker : Dr Keneiloe SIKHWIVHILU</i>	NIC DST/MINTEK
12:15 to 13:30	<i>Lunch break</i>	

Expertise and potential solutions

Chair/Moderators: A.Prof C. POCHAT & Prof NOMNGONGO

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation / Institute
13:30 to 13:50	Introduction to Process Energy Environment Technology Station (PEETS) and an overview of Effective Microorganisms in the treatment of Fresh water system. <i>Invited Speaker : Dr Kousar Banu HOORZOOK</i>	PEETS, UJ
13:50 to 14:10	A solution to save our drinking water resources: grey water recycling <i>Invited Speaker: Pierre MAGNES</i>	Firmus France
14:10 to 14:30	Urbanization & Decentralised Treatment of water: challenges to take up in order to enhance reuse & valorisation. <i>Invited Speaker: Prof. Marc HERAN</i>	IEM
14:30 to 14:50	Water Reuse Opportunities for Municipal and Industrial Players <i>Invited Speaker: Leon XU</i>	VEOLIA
14:50 to 15:10	Alternative Methods for Metals Recovery - Chemical Complexation and Extraction Technologies. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Stephane PELLET-ROSTAING</i>	ICSM
15:10 to 15:40	coffee break	
15:40 to 16:00	Organophosphorus compounds: synthesis, complexing abilities & applications. <i>Invited Speaker: Prof. Jean-Luc PIRAT</i>	ICG
16:00 to 17:00	Discussions around points raised during the day – conducted by Marc HERAN & colleagues	

Thursday, July 18 - SIMEV thematic school

Sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes - Energy supply

Presentation of challenges – focus on small-scale issues

Chair/Moderator: Prof RAMONTJA + P. MAGNES

9:00 to 9:10	Introduction & Presentation of the UNESCO SIMEV Chair <i>Invited Speaker: Mathilde BOUCHER</i>	SIMEV
9:10 to 9:40	Introduction to IEM - Expertise, know-how and facilities With a focus on nanostructured interfaces for membrane applications <i>Invited Speaker: Prof Philippe MIELE</i>	IEM
9:40 to 10:00	Water treatment issues in South African rural areas: overview of the context. <i>Invited speaker: Dr Somandla NCUBE</i>	UNISA
10:00 to 10:30	coffee break	

Expertise and potential solutions: part I

Chair/Moderator: Prof. PIRAT

10:30 to 10:50	Use of Local Clays for the Remediation of Ground Water in Rural Areas <i>Invited speaker: Dr Rabelani MUDZIELWANA</i>	University of Venda
10:50 to 11:20	Membrane technologies & Their Applications to the Mining Industry <i>Invited Speaker: A.Prof Céline POCHAT</i>	IEM
11:20 to 11:40	Polymer Nanocomposite Membranes and Resins Research for wastewater remediation. <i>Invited Speaker: A.Prof Richard MOUTLOALI</i>	University of Johannesburg
11:40 to 12:00	Innovative membrane processes coupling to face new water challenges <i>Invited Speaker: Dr François. ZAVISKA</i>	IEM
12:00 – 13:30	Lunch break	

Thursday, July 18 - SIMEV thematic school

Sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes - Energy supply

Expertise and potential solutions: part II

Chair/Moderator: A.Prof R.MOUTLOALI + Dr F. ZAVISKA

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation / Institute
13:30 to 13:50	Treatment of wastewater and effluent re-use in small communities <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Caliphs ZVINOWANDA</i>	University of Johannesburg
13:50 to 14:10	Membrane bioreactor for urinary nitrogen stabilization: microbial acclimation and system performance. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Geoffroy LESAGE</i>	IEM
14:10 – 14:30	Strong Institutional Arrangement for Sustainable Membrane Filtration Water Supply in Rural Communities: a case of Tshaanda, Limpopo, South Africa. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Fred MOLELEKWA</i>	TUT
14:30 to 14:50	Solar powered desalination units for small communities and remote locations: case study of plants located in Africa using the Osmosun® technology <i>Invited Speaker: Dr André DERATANI</i>	IEM/Mascara
14:50 – 15:20	coffee break	
15:20 -15: 40	Treatment of Water effluents and Water re-use Hair Saloon and personal care products. <i>Invited Speaker: Giovanna BENNETT (TBC)</i>	L’Oreal South Africa
15:40 – 16:40	Discussions around points raised during the day – conducted by Geoffroy Lesage & colleagues	
16:40 - 17:30	Poster Session	

Friday, July 19

Moderators: Dr MALINGA + S. PELLET-ROSTAING

Global environmental protection: Air quality

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation / Institute
9: 00 - 9:20	Air pollution and human health - a South African perspective <i>Invited Speaker: Bianca WERNECKE</i>	South African Medical Research Council
9:20 – 9:40	Performance Assessment of Metrobus Diesel Dual Fuel Buses towards a Soot Free Transport. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Samson MASEBINU</i>	PEETS, UJ
9:40 – 10: 00	Addressing air pollution in dense low-income settlements through air quality offsets. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Kristy LANGERMAN</i>	Department of Geography, UJ
10:00- 10:20	Molecular Filtration Media for Improved Air Quality. <i>Invited Speaker: Dr Abdoulaye DOUCOURE (TBC)</i>	Hollingsworth & Vose (HV) - USA
10:20 to 10:50	coffee break	

Potential collaborative projects & Conclusion

time	Presentation (title/topic)	Organisation / Institute
10:50 to 11:10	International training & cooperation tools available in Montpellier. <i>Invited Speaker: Prof. P. MIELE</i>	Montpellier University
11:10 to 11:30	Research support and international collaboration opportunities available at the University of Johannesburg. <i>Invited speaker: Dr Ndivhuwo LURULI & Lebethe MALEFO</i>	University of Johannesburg
11:30 to 11:50	Summary and conclusion: Future collaborative projects and overall perspectives. <i>Chair LOC (Prof. XY MBIANDA)/ Chair Mont. (Prof. P. MIELE)</i>	UJ / UM

Lunch break

Visit of UJ laboratories

Words of Welcome

Chair: **Prof Debra MEYER**

Executive Dean Faculty of Sciences - University of Johannesburg)

9:10 to 9:20

Professor Sinah SAURABH

Deputy vice Chancellor Research of the University of Johannesburg

9:20 to 9:30

Mr Mathieu BECUE

Attaché for Innovation - French Embassy in South Africa

9:30 to 9:40

Mr Khaya SISHUBA

Director: Bilateral Relations - Europe & Gulf States, Department of Science and Technology

Full name: KHAYA GOLDSWORTH SISHUBA

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Languages: English, Xhosa

ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL QUALIFICATIONS

Completed studies

- Master of Science in Industrial Strategy and Trade Policy, University of Manchester – United Kingdom, 2002. *Dissertation: Changing Role of Developmental State in Global Economics: A case of South Korea*
- Master in Diplomatic Studies, University of Pretoria, 2011. *Dissertation: Prioritising Diplomacy as an Instrument of the United States' Foreign Policy in the Aftermath of the 'War on Terror'*
- Post Graduate Diploma in Human Resources Management, University of Manchester – United Kingdom, 2000.
- Leadership and Economic Diplomacy – Civil Service College – Singapore, 2017.
- Executive Education Programme in Science, Technology and Innovation Policy, Harvard University – United States of America, 2006.
- B. Tech Degree in Public Management (Honours) University of South Africa, 1998.
- National Diploma in Public Management, Mangosuthu Technikon, 1993.

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

1. **DIRECTOR: BILATERAL RELATIONS – EUROPE AND GULF STATES - August 2006 – Present: Department of Science and Technology**
 - Initiate cooperation with countries in Europe and Gulf States in science and technology.

- Represent the Department in international engagements and support South African missions abroad in science and technology collaborations.
 - Represent South Africa on science and technology Joint Commissions and Bi-national Commissions at home and abroad.
 - Support political principals and departmental senior official in strategic engagement with international partners.
 - Develop strategies for international engagements in science and technology.
- 2. DEPUTY DIRECTOR: AFRICAN COOPERATION - April 2004 – May 2005: Department of Science and Technology**
- Negotiate and service Science and Technology bilateral agreements of mutual benefit on science and technology with African states.
 - Coordinating the DST international work with the Department of international relations and cooperation.
 - Represent DST in bilateral interaction with African states on science and technology cooperation.

He has represented the Department of Science and Technology on science partnerships with the following countries: *Lesotho, Mali, Kenya, Sweden, UK, Ireland, Denmark, Switzerland, Kazakhstan, Iran, Israel, France, Poland, Norway, Botswana, Zambia, Slovakia, Germany, Qatar, Oman, Belgium, Italy, Taiwan, Ireland, Zimbabwe, Jordan and Saudi Arabia.*

Steps to advance membrane & filtration sciences in Africa: Perspectives from the African Membrane Society

The African Membrane Society (AMSIC) vision is to train a critical mass of experts in the field of membrane science, filtration and sustainable energy technologies all across Africa. Fulfilling this vision requires a consistence willingness to identify and build collaboration with partners that share similar ideals in terms of facilitating clean water access, promoting affordable strategies for clean air quality, or improving patient protection in healthcare settings.

This presentation will give an opportunity to introduce AMSIC network and describe key initiatives undertaken since its inception in 2014. Topics covered will also highlight how international filtration venues held on the continent can help promote quality education in membrane science and foster socio-economic development benefiting communities in villages and urban centers.

Full name: DOUCOURE Abdoulaye (Ablo)

Title/position(s): Global Technology Manager (USA), President of the AMSIC (Mali)

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Short Biography

Ablo holds a PhD in Materials Chemistry from the University of Montpellier, France (ENSCM – 1995). He has spent over 20 years of his career conducting industrial research in the field of materials science and engineering to design advanced non-woven filtration and membrane products. He is Global Technology Manager at Hollingsworth & Vose (Virginia, USA), a world supplier of filtration and energy storage materials, which he joined in 2011. Ablo previously worked for 12 years at Pall Corporation (Port Washington, NY) where he developed new membranes for water, microelectronic and biopharmaceutical applications. He is co-founder and president of the African Membrane Society (AMSIC) and has chaired or co-organized several international scientific venues in Mali, Morocco, South Africa and Tunisia, since 2000. Ablo is also engaged in research and teaching activities at the University of Bamako (Faculté des Sciences & Techniques du Mali) and the Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs du Mali. He is the inventor of 5 patents supporting trademarked filter products, has written more than 30 publications and has been invited as plenary and keynote speakers for international conferences.

Non-occupational environmental risk assessment from exposure to mercury in the gold mining environment of Witwatersrand basin, South Africa

In the early days of gold mining, mercury was used to extract gold from pulverised mercury-gold amalgam. Although this process has long ceased, the tailings obtained after the separation of Hg from gold ores were deposited in impoundments for storage. The impoundments, therefore, can be said to represent a major source of mercury into the surrounding environment. The main objective of this study was to conduct a non-occupational environmental risk assessment of inhabitants living around the West Rand of Johannesburg in South Africa, from exposure to total mercury via water and sediment using the Risk-Integrated Software for Clean-ups.

Full name: NKWE Sylvester

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Short biography

Sylvester Nkwe completed a Master degree in Environmental Management, also certified as a member of the South Africa council for natural scientific professions. He has been working in the mining industry since 2003 under the Environmental Management field. For the past 15 years He has learned extensively about each environmental activities, aspects and impacts from the gold mining processes. He has experience and knowledge about mine environmental monitoring and modeling, projects licensing and permitting. Sylvester Nkwe is well versed in the development and implementation of ISO14001:2015. He is an experienced auditor of both environmental management systems and legal compliance.

Treatment of Brine for the Recovery of Drinking Water, Calcium Carbonate and Sodium Sulphate

Environmental laws everywhere today are meant to promote cleaner production, waste minimization, water reuse, recycling and waste treatment, with disposal seen as a last resort. South Africa's total waste stream amounts to 539 million t/a, of which industrial and mining waste amounts to about 487 million t/a (90%). Liquid and solid waste streams from water treatment processes need to be removed from site according to the zero waste principle. The purpose of our research is to evaluate and commercialize Freeze Crystallization and the ROC process (reverse osmosis combined with freeze-desalination), for the recovery of clean water and saleable products such as CaCO_3 , $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$. In this particular study the RO brine considered had a freezing point of -3° and ice crystallized at -1° . It was found that: (i) Pure ice with a TDS of less than 300 mg/L can be recovered from the RO brine with a TDS of 26 000 mg/L; (ii) The COP (coefficient of performance) of a laboratory scale freeze crystallization unit amounted to 0.5; (iii) The combined capital redemption and running costs for brine treatment with freeze crystallization totalled R80.00/m³; (iv) The combined capital redemption and running costs for brine treatment with the ROC (reverse osmosis/cooling) process amounted to R45.00/m³ and (v) Saleable products with a potential value of R32.00/m³ can be recovered with the ROC process.

Key words: Brine treatment, Freeze crystallization, Mine water, ROC process, Sodium carbonate, Sodium sulphate

Full name: MUJURU Munyaradzi

Title/position(s): Dr/ Senior Lecturer

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Short biography

Dr Munyaradzi Mujuru is an accomplished scientist, academic and researcher. His interests are multi-disciplinary research, particularly regarding environmental management issues, energy technologies development, commercialisation of research and global change. His research work has been published in various international journals. He obtained a PhD at Tshwane University of Technology (TUT) and master's and bachelor's degrees from the University of Zimbabwe. He worked at the Scientific and Industrial Research and Development Centre (SIRDC) in Zimbabwe as a research scientist in the field of energy technologies development and commercialisation. During his time at SIRDC and Masvingo Polytechnic, he led the team that pioneered research on the production of biofuels in Zimbabwe. He worked at TUT, where he managed the piloting and commercialisation of various technologies in wastewater remediation, including the successful commercialisation of the Acid Mine Drainage (AMD) treatment process that was developed and commissioned by TUT and Marlow Aquatec on the West Rand, South Africa. He is currently a senior lecturer at the University of Limpopo (UL) in the Department of Water and Sanitation, where he is the chairperson of the research committee, and is involved in various research projects, including sanitation and wastewater projects. Dr Mujuru is supervising a number of masters and doctoral students at UL and the University of South Africa (UNISA).

Circular Economy Model For Water And Wastewater Management

The current water and wastewater business cycle within the South African water sector is predominantly based on the linear economy approach. In order to address current and future water security challenges in a sustainable manner, there is a need to rethink the water and sanitation value chain and identify the role of innovation in transitioning to a circular economy. The transitioning to a circular economy within the South African water sector is in further support of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In this regard, opportunities for circular economy currently exist within the man-made water cycle, with wastewater as carrier of 50% to 100% of waste resources lost mostly as unrecovered water, energy and materials. On the other hand, the wastewater sector is also responsible for 3% of electricity consumption globally accounting for about 56% of the operational carbon footprint of urban water systems. For water utilities to transition to a circular economy, the use of three key interrelated pathways (water, material and energy pathways) to achieving circular economy principles in the water sector is key. Moreover, the role of innovation in transitioning to a circular economy has significant potential to of creating new business models and jobs, including developing new skills and investments in communities as well as reducing the carbon footprint, thereby mitigating the impacts of climate change. In this regard, it is key for municipalities to rethink their water and sludge management strategies, so that disruptive innovations are adopted to benefit from resource recovery in support of circular economy principles implementation within the South African water sector. This presentation provides some perspective on the circular economy model that can be used to transition to a circular economy within the South African water sector including examples that provides opportunities for the required transition.

Full name: John Ngoni ZVIMBA

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Short Biography

Dr John Ngoni Zvimba is currently with the South African Water Research Commission as Research Manager responsible for the sustainable wastewater management research portfolio. He holds a doctorate degree in Chemistry and has postdoctoral research experience in Bioprocess Engineering. His research areas of interest include sustainable municipal, industrial and mining wastewater treatment and management, focussing on beneficiation and volarization. Dr Zvimba has authored/co-authored over 20 peer reviewed publications, 1 book, 2 patents, several conference presentations and technical reports and supervised/co-supervised 4 MSc students. He is currently a member of the Water Institute of Southern Africa and International Water Association.

Title: Water Treatment Technologies Research and Development at the DST/Mintek Nanotechnology Innovation Centre

Water security is a critical challenge confronting Southern Africa in the 21st century; it impacts greatly on the region's social well-being, food security and economic growth. Water scarcity is being exacerbated by escalating demand due to increased urbanization, rising standards of living, unsustainable usage, high levels of wastages, and increasing pollution which renders water not fit for use.

The National Development Plan in line with the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (specifically SDG 3) aims for accessibility to clean drinking water for all by 2030. This presentation will thus give an overview of activities undertaken at the DST/MINTEK Nanotechnology Innovation Centre on Research and Development of technologies for water treatment, to address the scarcity of clean drinking water in the Southern Africa region towards achieving SDG 3.

Full name: Keneiloe Sikhwivhilu

Title/position: Principal Scientist

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Short Biography

Keneiloe Sikhwivhilu is a Principal Research Scientist at the DST/MINTEK Nanotechnology Innovation Centre, where she leads a dynamic team of engineers and scientists in R&D of water and wastewater treatment technologies. She has a PhD in Chemistry from the University of the Witwatersrand (South Africa), specializing in heterogeneous catalysis and nanotechnology. She obtained training at the University of Kentucky (UKY, USA) as part of her PhD studies, and Post-Doctoral training on water treatment membrane development from the University of California Los Angeles (UCLA, USA). Dr Sikhwivhilu's research interests are in nanotechnology and its application in water and wastewater treatment, water reclamation, and renewable energy. Dr Sikhwivhilu has served as a National Principal Investigator of the India Brazil South Africa Trilateral Initiative (IBSA) Nanotechnology Water Platform, and is currently leading a bilateral collaboration between South Africa and Zambia on the development of decentralized water supply systems for informal settlements in African cities.

Introduction to Process Energy Environment Technology Station (PEETS) and an overview of Effective Microorganisms in the treatment of fresh water system

PEETS was established in 2010 under the support of University of Johannesburg. PEETS is funded by Technology Innovation Agency (TIA), which is an agency of the Department of Science and Technology (DST). The primary mandate for PEETS is to contribute towards improving the competitiveness of industry and SMEs through the application of specialized knowledge, technology and facilitating the interaction between industry (especially SMEs) and academia to enable innovation and technology transfer to grow the green economy. The mission is providing technical oriented enterprise development support in the water, energy and environment sector through appropriate technological innovations to grow South Africa's socio-economy in a sustainable manner.

One of the projects to be undertaken in the water focus area is the use of Effective Microorganisms in the treatment of fresh water resources. An overview of the technology and its treatment application will be discussed.

Full name: HOORZOOK Kousar Banu

Title/position: Research coordinator

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Short Biography

Dr Kousar is a water and health specialist, she obtained her Doctorate degree in Biomedical Technology at UJ Faculty of Health Science. She has 15 years of experience in the field of Microbiology and Molecular biology in the water sector. She was awarded a Technology Innovation Seed fund to develop a mobile water testing laboratory; she is currently setting up a commercialization entity within UJ to commercialize her product. Currently works at Process Energy Environment Technology station (PEETS) as a research coordinator in the Water focus area. She leads a number of projects in monitoring water quality on potable and environmental water sources; the major project is setting up ISO 17025 UJ accredited water testing laboratories.

A solution to save our drinking water resources: grey water recycling

In 2050 70% of the population will be urban and we will have more than 9.5 billion inhabitants. If the temperature rises by 2°C, 43% of the world's population will lack water according to the UN. It is therefore increasingly essential, if not vital, to preserve our drinking water resources and, above all, to make consistent use of drinking water.

In this way, there is no denying that there is no point in using drinking water for toilet flush, laundry, floor cleaning and even showers. FGWRS develop a technology for grey water recycling which is derived from research work for the European Space Agency (ESA) carried out by FIRMUS France.

This process has been implemented since 2005 at the Concordia Franco-Italian Antarctic Research Station with more than 1,200 users since commissioning without any technical or sanitary incident. This process, which uses membrane techniques, recycles more than 80% of the grey water and therefore saves almost 50% of the daily drinking water consumption. Coupled with energy recovery it is also a renewable energy source.

Full name: MAGNES Pierre

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Short Biography

Pierre MAGNES holds a PhD in Biology from the Paul Sabatier University in Toulouse. He has always worked in the organization and coordination of projects in the world of agriculture and energy. Since 2011 he has been involved with Jean-Christophe LASSERRE in the development of FIRMUS France, which works on membrane techniques to treating, purifying, separating and recycling water and wastewater. In 2017 he created FGWRS in Monaco to develop FIRMUS France's specific know-how in the grey water recycling sector.

Urbanization & decentralised treatment of water: challenges to take up in order to enhance reuse and valorisation

Sustainable development is coming in the field of water treatment. Several hot topics as energy footprint, impact of wastewater reuse: risks for health (pathogenic micro-organisms and viruses) and for environment (salts, nutrients, micropollutants) are arriving powerfully. Urbanization and waste management must therefore consider wastewater as a source of secondary raw material and their treatment must be oriented towards the resource revolution and the search for circular economies. Indeed, wastewaters are an alternative source of water, nutrients and energy. The wastewater treatment plant for the future must therefore support this paradigm shift and be designed as a Resource Recovery STation (STARR) by integrating more sustainable processes (Innovative Treatments), cleaner water and valued resources. The energy needs of the STARR are specific to each of its unit operations and, if it is possible to fetch thermal or hydraulic energy in the wastewater, the development of anaerobic processes allows the production of biogas to consider a positive energy treatment system. It then remains to produce treated wastewater suitable for a second life. This second life can be (i) for agricultural use which implies to make reliable the sanitary quality of the water produced (Level A, French legislation) by developing effective steric barriers (Membranes), but also (ii) for direct recycling where it is necessary to develop technological bricks leading to the production of water with physicochemical qualities close to those required for drinking water. The presentation will focus on the choice and the definition of the technological bricks of their energy needs and the scientific stakes that will produce a water that meets the uses in terms of health risks (microbiological), environmental risks (micro-pollutants) or direct recycling (irrigation, groundwater recharge, direct recycling).

Full name: HERAN Marc

Title/position(s): Professor

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Short Biography

Dr Marc Heran is professor of Chemical Engineering at the European Membrane Institute, University of Montpellier (France). Its fields of expertise concern water and wastewater treatment, separation process, membrane separation, biological process and membrane bioreactors. He is a committee member of the IWA's specialist group on Membrane Bioreactor modelling and control. His research career focuses on process intensification by the help of membranes, membrane energy demand, and circular economy. The objectives are to explore reliable, efficient and sustainable intensive technologies for wastewater treatment tuned to good water quality production, molecules of interest extraction or reuse and sustainable energy generation.

Water Reuse Opportunities for Municipal and Industrial Players

Urbanisation presents a water security challenge to municipalities and industries. With population growing steadily across South African cities, it should be of top priority to improve our cities' resilience towards water shortages. There are much untapped opportunities for both municipal and industrial players to work towards this common goal. In fact, the best synergy is formed when treated municipal wastewater is upgraded for industrial reuse.

Given the abundant availability of seawater, seawater desalination is an obvious source to secure our future water supplies. However, extracting fresh water from seawater remains the most expensive per-unit cost of treatment available. Furthermore, while it plays an ever-increasing role in meeting our fresh water supply requirements, it does little to promote more sustainable, more environmentally friendly and less wasteful water use practices.

Recycling water from wastewater for reuse is a sustainable way to reduce fresh water consumption. This practice allows prioritisation of fresh water to meet drinking water needs and curtails wastewater discharges into the environment. In many forward-thinking companies and municipalities, water reuse systems are already in place, allowing these users to enjoy a guaranteed availability of water supply; substantially lower their water bill; supplement their profitability by harvesting valuable resources contained in wastewater; and practice more environmentally sound water usage operations.

There is no one specific technology/process for water reuse. The solution generally involves a combination of several processes and technologies depending on the wastewater quality, intended reuse application, space availability, etc. In this presentation, Veolia hopes to provide inspiration to all stakeholders by providing an overview of the opportunities and technologies that are currently available in the market.

Case studies of leading municipal and industrial reuse plants will be discussed. These include Goreangab Water Reclamation Plant (Namibia), Durban Water Recycling (SA), Mossel Bay Reuse Plant (SA), Sydney Quarter (Australia), Nestle Cero Aqua Plant (Mexico), Ambatovy Mine (SA).

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Short Biography

Leon is a member of Veolia Water Technologies' Industrial Competency Centre, a specialised department dedicated to bring leading-edge water treatment technologies and expertise from Paris to Africa. Through studies and audits, he has helped many industrial clients to develop sustainable water management practices and to identify reuse opportunities at their factories.

Alternative methods for Metal recovery – chemical complexation and extraction technologies

As the world moves towards a cleaner, greener future, the uses for strategic and noble metals are likely to increase rapidly and the rare earths supply crunch in 2010/2011 served as a wake-up call to businesses and governments, highlighting the fact that future strategic metals supply (not only rare earths) should not be taken for granted. To meet the challenges of dwindling resources and the growth of needs, mining, recycling or substitution appear to be essential levers either to extract metals from low grade ores, to recover material flows from production waste or treatment of more complex objects at the end of life. As a consequence, vast amounts of sulfide mining wastes are deposited all over the world, especially in derelict mines. The oxidation of sulfides contained in these wastes causes the acidification and everlasting metal pollution of water courses in the surrounding of mine sites. The improvement of the water quality in these catchments requires the urgent adoption of remediation treatment. These measures must be supported in a deep knowledge of metal fluxes from mining wastes to the environment in order to prioritize remedial actions. On the other hand, most recent remedial measures put into practice have been focused on the cover of these mine wastes to avoid AMD generation or the treatment of the resulting AMD. However, the adoption of more sustainable solutions to this environmental quandary is possible based on the circular economy principles and related extraction and purification hydrometallurgical processes.

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Currently Director of the ICSM, Stéphane is head of the “Laboratory of Ion Separation by self-assembled Molecular Systems” that he joined in January 2009 and where he initiated new topics in the field of synthesis, characterization and study of chelating agents and materials for nuclear waste reprocessing and strategic metal recycling/extraction from WEEE and ores. The 9 years before, Dr. Pellet-Rostaing was located at the “Institut de Chimie et Biochimie Moléculaire et Supramoléculaire” (Lyon University). Since he has integrated the CNRS in 2002, he strongly contributed to the development of new research and industrial/academic scientific collaborations (ORANO, CEA, TND, Rhodia, MERAL, ONIDOL, National Stach, Fuzhou University, Antananarivo University, Lebanon University, Huelva University, ICPE-Moscow). He published 123 articles in peer-reviewed international journals and 29 patents. Since 2015, he is the Scientific and Technical Manager of the French Laboratory of Excellence “LABEX ChemiSyst”, especially dedicated to the “strategic metal recycling and decontamination”.

Organophosphorus compounds: synthesis, complexing abilities & applications

Most of the phosphate rocks used commercially contain small quantities of metals such as uranium, lanthanides and yttrium and rare earth elements (REEs). During the phosphate processing, by reacting the phosphate rocks with sulphuric acid, 30% of lanthanide and yttrium and more than 80% of uranium, present initially in the rocks, end up in phosphoric acid. Also, retreatment of worn nuclear fuel needs to use new methods for the separation of minor actinides like neptunium, plutonium and americium in acid concentrates. In the same time, handling of these actinides supposes to be able to react in case of acute internal contamination.

Different polyphosphine oxides with ether linkage and with methylene group between two phosphorus were synthesized and evaluated from liquid-liquid extraction and from transport by supported liquid membranes. In decorporation experiments, some of the synthesized phosphonates exhibited *in vivo* uranyle complexation, as well as an increase in its urinary excretion. For the extraction of rare earth elements (REEs) from nitric acid solution we developed a series of specifically designed Task Specific Ionic Liquids (TSILs). Three families of TSILs were synthesized. In such compounds, the bisphosphonate moiety was in interaction or directly bounded to an imidazolium cation making the extractant an integral part of the hydrophobic phase. These compounds are still under evaluation.

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Short Biography

Jean-Luc PIRAT received his PhD in 1986 from the University of Montpellier under the supervision of Pr. P Geneste and D.R. J-M Kamenka. He moved to the USA at the University of Michigan for 2 years postdoc position with Pr Ed Domino working on the synthesis and biological study of compounds that have an interaction with neuro-excitatory amino acids. In 1990, He joined the group of Pr H-J Cristau at ENSCM and became full professor in 2005. His research interest is focused on phosphorus chemistry for life science applications (agro-chemical and medicinal chemistry) and on the development of new phosphorus molecules.

Sustainable clean water in small communities via membrane processes – Energy supply

The UNESCO SIMEV Chair and STM Thematic Schools

The SIMEV Chair - **Membrane Science Applied for the Environment** - is an international university partnership certified by UNESCO since 2004. Attached to the National School of Chemistry of Montpellier (ENSCM) and hosted by the European Institute of Membranes (IEM), SIMEV is part of the UNITWIN UNESCO Chairs program, which supports a network of more than 700 higher education institutions in 116 countries. Relying on the expertise of researchers, engineers and technicians from Montpellier, SIMEV connects the academic world (>25 academic partners on 4 continents), policy makers, technical companies and social actors **to develop membrane technologies for sustainable development**. It contributes to the SDGs through training activities, support for R&D projects and networking activities around this thematic.

The Membrane Science & Technology (STM) thematic schools represent one of the main activities of the Chair. Membrane technologies are widely used for water treatments and are currently encountering large development all around the world. In order to support their autonomous and controlled expansion in developing countries, STM Thematic Schools want to raise the awareness of manufacturers, local stakeholders and scientists to stimulate the implementation of membrane technologies. 17 STM thematic schools have already been organized in 11 different countries (Morocco, Tunisia, Algeria, Senegal, Serbia, France, Romania, Egypt, Vietnam, Mexico and Lebanon). The program is adapted to the framework of each hosting country, which chooses the main topic of the session, depending on its own needs and wishes. Thematic Schools are more than just another kind of scientific congresses: they aim for direct, immediate application. E.g.: implementation of 2 nanofiltration stations to defluorize water in Senegal (2007-2012, following the 4th STM thematic school), new collaboration with the Vietnamese Academy of Science and Technology started in 2011, inauguration of a water treatment unit using membrane technology and renewable energy in Al Annouar High School (Morocco, 2014, 15th STM thematic school).

www.unesco-simev.org

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Short Biography

Mathilde BOUCHER works for the UNESCO SIMEV Chair since April 2017. As a food engineer, she first worked two years in a veterinary lab in charge of improving food safety in collective catering. Attracted by multidisciplinary and multicultural dynamics, she became the vice-coordinator of the European research project AFTER (FP7. 2010-2014). In charge of the demonstration and dissemination activities, she developed her expertise in research project management and communication. Keeping close relationship with researchers, she now focuses on one main objective: to make the results of research understandable for all (scientists and non-scientists) and easier to be implemented through networking activities.

Introduction to IEM – Expertise, know-how and facilities

Founded in 1994, the "European Institute of Membranes" (IEM - Institut Européen des Membranes), is a reference laboratory at the international level in the field of membrane materials and processes. Its research objectives are based on a multidisciplinary and multi-scale approach, from the development and characterization of new membrane materials to their implementation in membrane processes (effluent treatment, gas separation, biotechnologies related to food science and health...). The strategy consists in: (i) designing and synthesizing a functional material capable of separating molecules of similar configurations, (ii) developing physicochemical and hydrodynamic operating conditions that best control the transport and transfer phenomena, (iii): develop high efficiency membrane modules, (iv) perform a scale change from the laboratory scale to the pre- or semi-industrial module. The IEM is deeply involved in training (e.g. EM3E-4SW – Erasmus Mundus Master in Membrane Engineering for Sustainable Development, European PhD EUDIME). The lab also participates in two Marie Curie International Training Networks and is an integrated actor of the Chemistry Balard Research Department.

Nanostructured interfaces for membrane applications

The most fundamental phenomena on the nanostructured membrane for energy, environmental and health applications are the control of interfaces. The performance of all those nanostructured membranes and devices can be improved or controlled by the enhanced geometric area of the nanostructured interfaces. In this respect, an accurate control of the geometry (size, porosity etc.) and interfaces is primordial to finding the delicate balance between large/control interface areas and efficient transport conditions. Here, we used different synthesis techniques such as atomic layer deposition (ALD), electrospinning, electrodeposition, nanospheres lithography etc. as the main tools for the creation of controlled nanostructured interfaces in which the geometry can be tuned accurately in order to design nanostructured membrane with controlled interfaces. We will show examples of how these methods can be used to create membrane for water treatment (by photocatalytic or electrofenton reaction) as well as membrane for osmotic energy in which the performance varies with the nanostructure morphologies and interfaces.

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Short Biography

Philippe MIELE received his PhD in Inorganic Chemistry in 1993 at the University of Montpellier. He became Professor at the University of Lyon in the Laboratory of Multimaterials and Interfaces, and Lab Head from 2003 up to 2010. In fall 2010, he joined the European Institute of Membranes, setting up a new group. In 2011, he has been appointed to his present position as Lab Head. Its research interests lie in boron chemistry, particularly for molecules and materials for energy, environmental and health applications. He is mostly recognized as an expert in the field of non-oxide advanced ceramics using the Polymer Derived Ceramics route. Philippe has co-authored around 260 papers in international journals (303 Scopus documents, H = 45), 12 patents and has given 42 invited talks in international meetings. He was nominated junior member (2003) then senior member (2016) of the "Institut Universitaire de France" (IUF) and has been elected in 2011 at the "World Academy of Ceramics" (class "Science"). Since June 2019, he is also the Director of the Chemistry Balard Research Department of the University of Montpellier.

Water treatment issues in South African rural areas: an overview of the context

One of South Africa's obligations summarized in Section 27(1) (b) of the Constitution is to ensure that all citizens have the right to sufficient water. While urban dwellers receive piped water treated using modern technologies, the major challenge faced by municipalities is in rural areas. The presentation therefore gives a *status quo* in terms of access to drinking water sources in the rural areas of South Africa. The presentation also looks at the Blue Drop Reports released annually by the Department of Water and Sanitation to address water quality and how it touches on problems faced in rural areas. The presentation gives an analysis of the treatment technologies that have been introduced in rural areas for processing alternative sources of drinking water. The capacity of various companies commissioned by the Department of Water Affairs to manage and supply rural areas and poor communities with clean water are analyzed. Technologies currently available for treatment of dam and river water for drinking purposes and accessible to the rural folk are assessed. Opportunities for more viable technologies introduced by academics and private companies including membrane technology are also discussed. The presentation also mentions the role of hygiene education initiatives and programs as well as the need to consider Indigenous Knowledge Systems in addressing the water treatment issues in South African rural areas.

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Short Biography

Dr Somandla Ncube is a postdoctoral research fellow at University of South Africa. He did his postgraduate studies at University of the Witwatersrand where he graduated BSc Hons (2013), MSc *cum laude* (2016) and PhD (2018) with specialization in Environmental Analytical Chemistry. He has already published 14 articles and 2 book chapters. In 2018 he was awarded the prestigious SACI postgraduate medal for his PhD work. Currently, his research focus is on development and advancement of sample preparation techniques for analysis of organics in water and plant samples followed by quantitation using the high-tech GCxGC-HRT and LC-Orbitrap/MS instruments.

Use of Local Clays for the Treatment of Surface and Ground Water in Rural Areas

Majority of people in rural South Africa depend on groundwater as the main source of water for domestic purposes. However, groundwater in Limpopo, North West and Northern Cape is reported to have high levels of chemical species such as fluoride. High fluoride in drinking water has health and social implications. Apart from fluoride groundwater is sometimes contaminated with pathogens which accounts for the death of thousands of children worldwide annually. As such there is need to develop low cost and sustainable technologies for water at household level suitable for rural households. The use of clay and clay minerals in water treatment has gained worldwide attention due to their physicochemical properties that enables them to adsorb toxicants from water via physical processes such as ion exchange. Furthermore, clays are easily available at little or no cost in most rural environments. Moreover, clay surfaces can be modified to enhance their sorption capacity for chemical contaminants in water. Our research group has evaluated the use of various locally available clayey materials and diatomaceous earth for use in water treatment. Materials were modified with various metal oxides to enhance their contaminants removal efficiency. This presentation will show the overview of the work we have done using clay and clay minerals for groundwater treatment and further show the current developments and challenges in relations to applications of materials at household level.

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Short Biography

Dr. Rabelani Mudzzielwana is a young postdoctoral candidate at the University of Venda, Department of Ecology and Resource Management working under the mentorship of Professor Mugera Gitari. His research niche area is development of clay based and Nano materials for surface and groundwater treatment, phytoremediation and development of acid mine drainage treatment technologies. Dr. Mudzzielwana currently has more than 10 publications including peer reviewed articles, conference proceedings and book chapter.

Membrane technologies & Their Applications to the Mining Industry

The Mining industry is often associated with negative consequences on the environment. It generates acid mine drainage (AMD) and effluents containing cyanides that have long-term impact on aquatic organisms, plant growth and human health. Mining Industry uses large amount of water and implementing membrane technologies for water reuse participate to a sustainable management by recycling a becoming rare resource and reducing polluted wastewater. Membrane processes can also act in resource recovery for sulfuric acid, metals and potential rare earth elements retrieval.

There is a great variety in membrane processes depending on the membrane morphology and on the applied driving force. The membrane performance in operating conditions can be evaluated by calculated parameters, helping for the selection of the right membrane process. Nanofiltration and reverse osmosis are presented as conventional membrane processes for mining industry. Forward osmosis and membrane distillation display alternatives. However for a better use of these technologies, integrated processes can be implemented to remove substances that produce the fouling before the recovery of heavy metals and/or the generation of clean water.

The European Institute of Membrane in Montpellier (France) offers a wide range of facilities to study membrane and membrane processes. Innovative membrane systems can be prepared and integrated in membrane pilot (UF, NF, RO, MD). The membrane material can be characterized and the membrane performance evaluated.

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Short Biography

Céline POCHAT-BOHATIER obtained her PhD in Chemical Engineering from the University of Montpellier (France) in 1999. She has been working as Associated Professor at University of Montpellier (France) since 2000. She got her accreditation to supervise research in 2010. She is responsible of a team (M2Lab) working at the interface between academic and industrial research on the development of innovative hollow fiber membranes for water and gas treatment and on the control of their porous morphology in relation with their performances. She is the author and co-author of 53 publications, 3 book chapters, 3 patents, and 9 invited talks (H-index=14).

Polymer Nanocomposite Membranes and Resins Research for wastewater remediation

Demands on water filtration membranes to perform at certain levels is the current driver in membrane materials innovation. High selectivity at relatively elevated permeate flux is a topical area that our group is currently involved in. This has resulted in different approaches being explored in our laboratory to enhance important membrane performance parameters such as permeate flux, solute rejection and fouling propensity. The presentation will discuss progress within the laboratory. The work done in the past three years, specifically reviewing results from two different approaches to the subject, will be presented. In the first instance, chemical grafting of pH sensitive functional groups will be compared to the results on inclusion of tailored nanofillers in increasing rejection while maintaining a relatively unchanged permeate flux under similar operating conditions. The presentation will then conclude by giving a brief summary of results in modulating selectivity of adsorbent resins towards cyanide ions sequestration from water.

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Short Biography

Richard is Associate Professor in the Department of Chemical Sciences, University of Johannesburg, since January 2016. His research interests are in developing polymeric nanocomposite membranes and resins for wastewater remediation and water treatment. He previously worked at Mintek, an State Owned Enterprise developing metallurgical technologies and solutions where he spent ten years. He collaborates with industry on different solutions for wastewater treatment and developing new materials. He obtained his PhD from University of the Western Cape (UWC, 2003) followed by a postdoctoral fellowship at the University of the Witwatersrand (WITS, 2004) and later a visiting research fellow at Cranfield University, UK (2009).

Innovative membrane processes coupling to face new water challenges

Climate change, population growth, industrialization... are such critical factors affecting water resources, water supply and wastewater management. This presentation will be focused on the implementation of innovative treatment strategies in order to tackle some of these new water challenges. Two research projects conducted at the European Membrane Institute will be presented. The first one is related to the optimization of a hybrid process combining electrodialysis (ED) with nanofiltration (NF) for the treatment of surface water (Delta Meakong, Vietnam) contaminated by both pesticide and high salinity (sea water intrusion). The strategy consists at using ED process at a first stage for salinity removal in order to improve, in the second stage, the performance of NF system for pesticide removal. At which point ED desalination should be carried out in order to remove efficiently the pesticide and salinity in the second stage (NF) at a reasonable cost? To answer this question, an experimental design methodology (RSM) has been employed in order to describe and optimize the entire ED-NF hybrid system.

The second project is related to wastewater management in confined environment. More specifically, it consists to recycle water from urine coming from source separated toilet inside the train. The main objective is to develop a treatment strategy based on (1) the urine composition, (2) the treatment objective and (3) taking into account the specific constraint of the project. This strategy is based on a membrane bioreactor in order to treat COD and stabilized nitrogen (Nitrification) followed by electrodialysis for salinity regulation and then electrooxydation as a polishing process for eliminate bacteria, COD and remaining of ammonia. The question is how to operate these 3 processes in order to satisfy the objective of treatment?

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François Zaviska (34 years old) is assistant professor at University of Montpellier in the European Membrane Institute since September 2015. He obtained his PhD in Water Sciences in 2011 at the National Institute of Scientific Research (INRS-ETE) in Quebec City. His PhD thesis was focused on the treatment of organic micropollutants using electro-oxidation process. Then, in 2011, he worked as a post graduate at the European Membrane Institute on a membrane bioreactor process for the removal of pharmaceutical pollutants. He also worked two years from 2012 to 2014 as a research associate at University of South Australia (UniSa) in Adelaide. His researches at UniSa were related to the development of an efficient desalination process combining forward osmosis and reverse osmosis. His field of expertise concern water treatment processes such advanced oxidation processes, biological treatment and membrane desalination.

Treatment of wastewater and effluent re-use in small communities

Small communities are groups of people who live outside urban settings. These small communities are usually rural villages, farm settlements, commercial properties such as lodges, filling stations, restaurants in remote areas such as freeways, safari and game areas. The source of potable water in such areas is usually groundwater and the effluent are also at times released into the ground without any treatment, thus increasing the chances of groundwater pollution. A few of such settlements have capacity to hire sewage collectors who will then deliver it to the nearest municipal wastewater treatment works for treatment.

The Applied Water Research Group at UJ is investigating the use of advanced oxidation as an alternative sustainable process to sterilize the sewage effluent released by small communities. The aim is to use advanced oxidation chemicals such as sodium ferrate produced from sodium hypochlorite, ferric chloride and sulphuric acid. The target is to generate effluent which can be used for irrigation within the environment it has been generated.

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Short Biography

Dr. Caliphs Zvinowanda holds two Masters (Analytical Chemistry and Project Management) and a De-Tech (Environmental Chemistry) from Tshwane University of Technology. His research interests are mainly in water and wastewater treatment, sludge processing and recovery of commercial by-products from acid mine drainage sludge (yellow boys). At UJ, Dr Zvinowanda is initiating a research group focusing on Applied Water Research. The processes of interest including advanced oxidation, adsorption, and process chemistry in water and wastewater treatment.

Membrane bioreactor for urinary nitrogen stabilization: microbial acclimation and system performance

Urine source separation is of high interest because most of the nutrients in wastewater (WW) derive from urine and itself only accounts for less than 1 % of the total volume of WW. Separating urine from WW would offer various advantages: smaller scale, less energy consumption and production of an effluent of excellent quality for further water reuse strategy. Membrane bioreactors (MBR) have become a state-of-the-art technology for WWT. The specificity of having urine as the main source of nutrients is a low carbon to nitrogen ratio ($C/N < 2$) and a relatively high concentration in different salts above 10 g/L. Thus, the success of MBR operation would be really challenging. Indeed, if the low organic carbon load is very favorable to the nitrification stage, it is a significant barrier for a full denitrification and impact also the total nitrogen removal of treated water. Consequently, there is a risk of accumulating reaction intermediates such as nitrites NO_2^- . The overall objective is thus to investigate the feasibility of operating a MBR for urine treatment in terms of permeate quality. The activated sludge acclimation and membrane fouling were also particularly analyzed. This study showed that yellow water treatment may be possible by a membrane bioreactor even at low C/N ratio thanks to careful sludge acclimation and process parameters control.

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Dr. Geoffroy Lesage received his PhD from the National Institute of Applied Science of Toulouse (2009), where he studied an **hybrid wastewater treatment process associating adsorption onto activated carbon and biodegradation for hazardous micropollutants removal**. In 2012, Geoffroy became Associate Professor at the **European Membrane Institute (IMemEau group, Membrane Engineering Department)** at Montpellier University where he develops synergistic membrane and biodegradation strategies for wastewater streams. Specific research areas include **wastewater treatment, adsorption, biological process modelling, membrane biological reactors, dissolved organic matter characterization and micropollutants** issues (chemical analysis and toxicity assessments).

Strong Institutional Arrangement for Sustainable Membrane Filtration Water Supply in Rural Communities : a case of Tshaanda, Limpopo, South Africa

The presentation is based on the installation of a gravity-driven UF system in a small village that has approximately 600 inhabitants. It covers the processes followed and the commitment by various stakeholders towards ensuring the acceptance of the system by the community and sustainable supply of clean water to the community. The major stakeholders include KU Leuven (i.e., University in Belgium), Vhembe District Municipality, Tshwane University of Technology, Traditional Council and Community in Tshaanda. KU Leuven provided funding for the procurement and installation of the UF system, which has the capacity to provide 5KL/day. Tshwane University of Technology provided funding for water quality analysis. Vhembe district municipality took the responsibility of providing diesel for the engine that was pumping water from the fountain to the UF system. On the other hand, Tshaanda community made in-kind contribution, which included security and land for the system, operation and maintenance of the system.. The traditional council played a major role in ensuring that the system was accepted and embraced by the community. The UF system was installed within the primary school premises. For the past five years, since its installation in 2014, the system is still operating well, no parts have been replaced and the water quality is still within the recommended standard. This is attributed to the cooperation and commitment by all the relevant stakeholders and the overall institutional arrangement.

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Dr Molelekwa is the founder of Gomotsegang Consultancy, a company that provides professional services in the fields of health and environment. Dr Molelekwa is a Research and Innovation Associate at Tshwane University of Technology in the Faculty of Science. He holds ND Public Health; NHD Public Health; B-Tech Environmental Health (Tshwane University of Technology); MSc Environmental Management (University of the Free State) and PhD Chemical Engineering (KU Leuven). Dr Molelekwa has extensive experience in environmental health and management field. He has supervised research projects for post graduate students (i.e., MSc and B-Tech.). He also wrote book and has also published his research work in peer reviewed journals and presented at local and international conferences. Dr Molelekwa has two patents to his name.

Solar powered desalination units for small communities and remote locations: case study of plants located in Africa using the Osmosun® technology

The areas of zones concerned by water scarcity are expanding all around the world due to the continuously increasing demand for fresh water. Membrane desalination of seawater for coastal areas and of brackish ground waters for inland locations is generally considered as one of the technologies capable for solving this issue. Two main causes can be identified including physical scarcity as in arid and semi-arid regions and lack of infrastructures as in developing countries and remote areas. It is now accepted that integration of desalination with renewable energy (RE) sources is the best solution to supply fresh water of good quality for small to medium communities.

This presentation will focus on the use of solar generator using photovoltaic (PV) panels to power membrane desalination plant. The first part will be devoted to the specific constraints of this technology with respect to the fluctuations and intermittence of the solar irradiance and to the strategies that can be developed to smooth the energy variations. Population in many areas of Africa suffers of water shortage due to periodic and prolonged droughts that requires treating unconventional water sources such as desalination of seawater and of brackish water. The lack of energy supply is also often a major restriction to apply the usual desalination technology. Case studies of desalination plants equipped with the Osmosun® technology from Mascara Renewable Water (Fig. 1) will be detailed in the second part.

The Osmosun® unit set up in 2018 at Witsand (Hessequa, W. Cape Province, South Africa) is the first example of solar seawater desalination without use of electrical storage device in Africa. It can daily produce 100 m³ of fresh water powered by 100% solar energy and up to 350 m³ coupled to the grid. The water demand of the community is presently of 150 m³ primarily produced with solar energy in hybrid operation. The overall energy consumption of the unit including the water pretreatment is about 3 kWh/m³ that is one of the lower levels of energy consumption for RE desalination technology.

Another example is the Osmosun® units (also set up in 2018 in the Gaza Province Mozambique) designed to supply drinking water to about 7000 inhabitants split over 6 villages. The cumulated daily production is about 145 m³ obtained by desalting brackish groundwater (salinity of 2 to 5 g/L). 4 of the 6 units are stand-alone desalination systems without battery; the 2 others are connected to the grid.

M.A. Kammoun¹, S. Gassara¹, C. Antonelli¹, A. Deratani¹, T. Garel², M. Haudebourg² and M. Vergnet²
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Dr André Deratani joined in 1995 the European Membrane Institute (IEM) in Montpellier (France), became CNRS Senior Scientist in 1999 and is Emeritus since 2017. His main research activities are in the domains of polymer chemistry and physical chemistry for application in functional materials in the form of beads and films. His current topics include the preparation of novel materials and engineered interfaces with applications in water and wastewater treatment with a strong emphasis on desalination and membrane technology powered with renewable energy..

Air pollution and human health - a South African perspective

The state of ambient air quality in South Africa is topical, controversial and regularly discussed in the media. Just over a month ago, environmental groups decided to take National Government to High Court over the violation of our Constitutional Right to clean air. Air pollution levels on the Mpumalanga Highveld are compared to those of China, and the area has been termed “the world’s largest air pollution hotspot”. In a country which relies mainly on coal-fired power stations to meet its energy demands, the impact that the coal mining- and electricity industry has on air quality and consequently on human health cannot be ignored. Air pollution is deemed a “silent killer” which prematurely claims up to 7 million lives a year, including the lives of 600 000 children. Exposure health effects range from increased hospital admissions and emergency room visits, to increased risk of premature death. Deaths attributed to air pollution are mainly from heart disease, stroke, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, lung cancer, and acute respiratory infections in children. The health burden of dirty air is inequitably placed upon those most vulnerable: the marginalized, the poor, the sick, the young and the elderly. In South Africa, this is particularly applicable in many low- income communities living near air pollution sources such as mines, industries and busy roads. It is equally applicable to communities where reliance on domestic burning practices for cooking and heating purposes creates high levels of indoor air pollution. The SAMRC conducts research into impacts of air pollution from different sources on human health to better understand the importance of the prevention, reduction and adequate management of air pollution in the South African context. It does this with the hope of influencing policy to ultimately reduce the air pollution health burden placed on the South African populace.

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Short Biography

Bianca is a project manager in the Environment and Health Unit of the South African Medical Research Council. She conducts and manages research that looks at health effects of air pollution and the impacts of household air pollution interventions. She spent 7 years in the air quality space of the South African energy sector where she advised the country’s power stations on matters relating to air quality management and compliance and where she formed part of a team pioneering air quality offsets in South Africa. Bianca’s air quality interests led her to study exposure to air pollution in low-income communities.

Performance Assessment of Metrobus Diesel Dual Fuel Buses towards a Soot Free Transport

The City of Johannesburg Metrobus Dedicated Dual Fuel (DDF) initiative began in 2013 with the aim to reduce operational cost mainly contributed by the cost of fuel, and the greenhouse emission from the City Metro transport department. A total of 150 buses were procured in as part of this initiative. These buses have been operational for about four years now and have covered more than 90,000 KM each. It is however known to Metrobus that the anticipated reduction in diesel consumption is not reflective rather the operational cost due to fuel is on the increase. Furthermore, it has been stated in previous operational report that the DDF buses are not being used to their maximum benefit with some buses haven't been fueled with CNG over the past 20 months. This brings to question what the limitations are being faced by Metrobus hindering its operational efficiencies towards maximizing the potential of these buses. Hence, there is a need to assess the performance of these buses against a benchmark, understand the existing limitations and proffer solutions to enhance their operational performance. Aside operational inefficiencies, the Metrobus fleets consist of ageing vehicles and there is need to replace some of the old vehicles which are becoming uneconomical to maintain. For the City of Johannesburg to fulfill part of its C-40 commitment and reduce the over greenhouse gas emission footprint, the future buses must have a significantly reduced emission factor and possibly a soot free technology. Therefore, towards achieving the reduced greenhouse emission, while still meeting local and country objectives, there is need for fleet renewal planning, strategy for implementation and optimization of the fleet strength.

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Short Biography

Samson is a multi-disciplinary professional with keen interest in biological and other forms of renewable energy, process integration, data analytics and economic modelling. He has more 11 years combined experience in mechanical and chemical engineering fields with special on bioenergy research, solar PV, energy storage, environmental performance of transport technologies and project development. Also, from previous projects with data analytics and economic modelling, he has gained knowledge in valuing equity and debt, to determining the levelised cost across portfolios and optimal decision criteria with appropriate econometrics. His skill sets are in the areas of waste to energy systems, process simulation, academic and technical reports writing, system evaluation and optimization. He is presently leading a project for the design, specification and construction of a 50 ton/day waste to biomethane plant for the City of Johannesburg.

Addressing air pollution in dense low-income settlements through air quality offsets

The worst air quality in South Africa is found in dense, low-income residential settlements. Residents of these areas are typically unable to afford or do not have access to sufficient clean energy like electricity or liquid petroleum. Housing is typically not insulated and poorly constructed, requiring large amounts of energy for heating in winter. Refuse is often collected at intervals of many months, resulting in large piles of waste accumulating in open spaces and eventually being burnt for hygiene reasons. Roads are often unpaved. These circumstances result in emissions of air pollution from a multitude of sources. Low-income households also often only have access to inferior health services, exacerbating their vulnerability to poor air quality. Air quality offsets are one of the mechanisms that have been introduced in South Africa to address the disproportionate impact of poor air quality on the poor. Air quality offsets are defined as “interventions specifically implemented to counterbalance the adverse and residual environmental impact of atmospheric emissions in order to deliver a net ambient air quality benefit within, but not limited to, the affected airshed where ambient air quality standards are being or have the potential to be exceeded and where opportunities and need for offsetting exist”. In this presentation, further background will be provided on air quality in low-income settlements in South Africa, and the design of air quality offsets projects. The emission testing facility at UJ’s Process, Energy and Environmental Technology Station (UJ-PEETS) is already equipped to support the air quality offsets roll-out by measuring emissions from solid and liquid fuel-burning stoves, and has plans to install a combustion chamber to enable the measurement of emission factors for waste and other materials.

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Short Biography

Dr Kristy Langerman is a senior lecturer at the Department of Geography, Environmental Management and Energy Studies at the University of Johannesburg, where she coordinates the Energy Studies Honours programme. She obtained her PhD from the University of the Witwatersrand in 2003, and conducted postdoctoral research at the National Centre for Atmospheric Research in Colorado. In 2005 she moved to Eskom’s Research Centre, where she headed up numerous air quality research projects. From 2008, she managed the Air Quality Centre of Excellence at Eskom’s Environmental Management Department. While there, Dr Langerman spearheaded Eskom’s programme to transition low-income households on the South African Highveld from coal to cleaner sources of energy. Her research interests include sustainable energy and air quality, particularly in the context of low-income communities. She was the President of the National Association for Clean Air (NACA) from 2012 to 2014 and is an editor of the Clean Air Journal.

Molecular Filtration Media for Improved Air Quality

According to the World Health Organization [1], 92% of human population inhale polluted air (representing 6.9 billion people), while each year more than 6 million fatalities are related to air contamination from fine particles –below 10 microns- and hazardous gases – NO_x, SO₂, H₂S, formaldehyde, Volatile Organic Compounds (VOC's), NH₃, O₃ and CO₂ [2]. Consistent exposure to poor air quality can lead to chronic health diseases such as bronchitis, asthma, allergies, and under more severe circumstances cancer or apoplexy.

This presentation will highlight key features of HV products designed to improve indoor air quality by simultaneously capturing harmful airborne particulate as well as vapors and gases originating from Volatile Organic Compounds, acidic or alkaline agents, aldehyde substances and its derivatives.

[1]: World Health Organization, 2016

[2]: World Health Organization, 2011 - 2016

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Short Biography

Ablo holds a PhD in Materials Chemistry from the University of Montpellier, France (ENSCM – 1995). He has spent over 20 years of his career conducting industrial research in the field of materials science and engineering to design advanced non-woven filtration and membrane products. He is Global Technology Manager at Hollingsworth & Vose (Virginia, USA), a world supplier of filtration and energy storage materials, which he joined in 2011. Ablo previously worked for 12 years at Pall Corporation (Port Washington, NY) where he developed new membranes for water, microelectronic and biopharmaceutical applications. He is co-founder and president of the African Membrane Society (AMSIC) and has chaired or co-organized several international scientific venues in Mali, Morocco, South Africa and Tunisia, since 2000. Ablo is also engaged in research and teaching activities at the University of Bamako (Faculté des Sciences & Techniques du Mali) and the Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs du Mali. He is the inventor of 5 patents supporting trademarked filter products, has written more than 30 publications and has been invited as plenary and keynote speakers for international conferences.

International training & cooperation tools available in Montpellier

The desire of the Montpellier chemists to work within a common federative structure is at the origin of the creation of the Chemistry Balard Research Department, founded in 2007 by the University of Montpellier, Montpellier National School of Chemistry, CNRS and CEA. Its mission is to harmonize the training offer between the partner institutions, as well as the research policy of the Institutes. The cluster brings together more than 400 permanent researchers and teacher-researchers in 4 research institutes: the Institute Charles Gerhardt Montpellier (ICGM - Institute for Molecular Chemistry and Material Sciences), the Institute of Biomolecules Max Mousseron, the European Institute of Membranes (IEM) and the Institute for Separation Chemistry in Marcoule (ICSM). It also relies on various tools such as the Doctoral School "Chemical Sciences - Balard" (ED 459), the LabEx "CheMiSyst", the Carnot Institute "Chemistry Balard -CIRIMAT", 3 technical platforms and 2 international chairs.

Today as part of MUSE I-SITE project - Montpellier University of Excellence, the main objective of the Chemistry Balard department is to support the development of training, research and innovation for economic development in the field of chemistry. These objectives are based on 3 main themes: (i) Energy, materials and its vectors, (ii) Valorization of natural resources and processes of sustainable chemistry, (iii) Health and human protection. They also contribute to the success of the MUSE project by developing interfaces with other disciplines around the three major societal challenges: Feed, Protect, Care.

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Short Biography

Philippe MIELE received his PhD in Inorganic Chemistry in 1993 at the University of Montpellier. He became Professor at the University of Lyon in the Laboratory of Multimaterials and Interfaces, and Lab Head from 2003 up to 2010. In fall 2010, he joined the European Institute of Membranes, setting up a new group. In 2011, he has been appointed to his present position as Lab Head. Its research interests lie in boron chemistry, particularly for molecules and materials for energy, environmental and health applications. He is mostly recognized as an expert in the field of non-oxide advanced ceramics using the Polymer Derived Ceramics route. Philippe has co-authored around 260 papers in international journals (303 Scopus documents, H = 45), 12 patents and has given 42 invited talks in international meetings. He was nominated junior member (2003) then senior member (2016) of the "Institut Universitaire de France" (IUF) and has been elected in 2011 at the "World Academy of Ceramics" (class "Science"). Since June 2019, he is also the Director of the Chemistry Balard Research Department of the University of Montpellier.

Research support and international collaboration opportunities available at the University of Johannesburg

The University of Johannesburg's (UJ) Strategic Plan *commits the university to distinguished scholarship and reputable research and innovation, and to the promotion of internationally competitive research as a core strategic goal*. Central to the achievement of this critical goal is the provision of adequate funding. As such, one of the University's Strategic Research Goals is to "increase, manage and structure the external and internal funding for research". The University's Research & Innovation Division is the custodian of research support, including the provision of funding opportunities for the UJ community. Nationally, the university facilitates access to external funding from the National Research Foundation (NRF), the country's largest funding agency supported by the government. The University also provides access to funding provided by international donors, with some of this funding awarded as part of collaborative research projects between UJ-based researchers and partners based abroad.

More international opportunities and support, such as international mobility grants, are provided to academics and students by the University's Internationalisation office. Through internationalisation, the University of Johannesburg is poised to enhance its scholarly engagement and impact on national, regional, and continental transformation agendas, as well as to position the University on the global higher education landscape. The work undertaken by the Division for Internationalisation is central to the UJ's vision of 'an International University of choice, anchored in Africa, dynamically shaping the future'.

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Dr Ndivhuwo Luruli is the Director: Strategic Research Support at the University of Johannesburg (UJ). Prior to joining UJ, Dr Luruli was appointed as Director: BRICS & Research at the National Institute for the Humanities and Social Sciences (NIHSS). She has also worked for the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET), and the National Research Foundation (NRF).

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Mr Lebeth Malefo was appointed as Director: Study Abroad in 2012. Since 2 January 2018, Mr Malefo has been in the position of Acting Executive Director: Internationalisation to which the portfolios of International Student Recruitment, Admissions and Marketing, Study Abroad and Academic Services report.